

COMPARATIVE STUDY REGARDING STUDENTS' PERCEPTION ON EDUCATIONAL SERVICES PROVIDED BY INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

Purpose – This paper aims to reach two coordinates: identifying the determinant factors for increasing international students' satisfaction with the educational service provided by the host university, on one hand, and advancing a set of measures that could increase this satisfaction, on the other hand.

Methodology/approach – The applied research method consists in the comparative analysis of different results obtained by various previous researches, based on the application of the SERVQUAL model in universities from different areas of the world, with the aim of determining international students' perceptions regarding the quality level of the received educational service.

Findings – The paper emphasizes the determinant factors for increasing international students' satisfaction with educational services and the measures that once adopted could increase their satisfaction.

Research limitations/implications – The sample of universities taken into account for the study is relatively small and therefore the obtained results cannot be extrapolated to the majority of foreign students that study at universities abroad.

Practical implications – The study highlights those elements that could lead to the improvement of quality management in a higher education institution.

Originality/value – It is a specific study that could help stakeholders to acknowledge the importance of the foreign student's perceptions about the quality of university management.

Key words: service quality measurement, quality management, higher education.

Introduction

Education has become nowadays one of the most important sources for the global economy. Higher education is expected to have great contributions due to the high impact it has on every nation's economy. Higher education institutions face a very intense competition, which requires the sustained improvement of their educational services, in order to attract a high as possible number of local students, but especially foreign ones. The latter ones represent a valuable source of revenue and at the same time, they are true catalysts for increasing the reputation of the respective universities. To reach this goal, they seek to harmonize the standards, to deepen the mechanisms for quality assurance and to acknowledge professional qualifications. In the same context, it has to be brought into discussion the academics' efforts, which try to continuously improve the teaching and learning methods, given the requirement to align them to the significant changes that all educational systems face under globalization and technological progress. With the enhancement of globalization of higher education and of the competition on the educational international market implicitly, universities are challenged to positively influence whenever possible the level of satisfying the needs of international students by increasing the quality of the provided services. Students' feedback represents an important requirement for capturing the information that can correctly guide the quality assurance process in higher education. Moreover, current students are more aware of consumer rights and of information and claims issued by the current labor market. Hence service quality measurement has become more imperative than ever. However,

the quality of services provided by higher education institutions cannot be measured objectively, because it is a complex and varied concept, which needs to be continuously explored, being essential for:

- attracting a larger number of students;
- ensuring an efficient development of human capital, in the absence of which economic progress would not be possible;
- helping the decision factors to identify and implement on time those strategic measures that bring value to the educational environment, transforming them into true opportunities for the higher education institution. All these will make a positive mark on the effectiveness of each university's offer and the quality of the provided services will be improved.

The aim that was sought by comparing studies conducted in different universities in the world on the opinion of international students related to the received educational services has two coordinates:

1. identifying those dimensions proposed by the SERVQUAL model that should be the most and most often prioritized and stimulated in order to achieve a high as possible level of student satisfaction;
2. determining a set of measures that could reduce or even help eliminate the gaps that affect student satisfaction with the educational service quality.

All these preoccupations were determined by the interest of emphasizing those ways by which students from various countries can be attracted to university studies in the conditions of an extremely competitive and versatile international education market, with them also being important sources for the host country's budget. Probably the best example in this respect is that of Australia, one of the countries that annually attracts most of the international students and this has generated in 2018 34,9 billion USD for the country's economy (Study International, 2019).

Methodology

The basis of this analysis consists of researches conducted by foreign researchers in other countries. These studies have emphasized the local situation regarding the dimensions of the SERVQUAL model and highlighted those elements considered as being the most important for the investigated students for choosing a university and also for continuing the studies started there.

The instrument used for analyzing each university included in the present study is the SERVQUAL model which is considered an instrument that enables a good knowledge of students' opinion about the educational services provided by the university. This model consists in questioning students through 22 statements regarding their perceptions on the quality of the received service, as well as through 22 statements regarding their expectations about this service's quality. The respondents are asked to evaluate those statements using a Likert scale. These statements are grouped into the following dimensions (Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1988):

- **Tangibles** that emphasize the existence of physical aspects that are specific for the educational service adapted to present days;
- **Reliability** reflects the university's ability of safely and correctly providing the promised services, even if these are performed for the first time and of respecting the established time frames;
- **Responsiveness** reflects the consistency of the academics' performance;
- **Assurance** is expressed through the academics' training, their professional ability of delivering high quality services, through the politeness, respect and consideration that the staff shows towards the student, or in other words, assurance is expressed through the knowledge and courtesy of the staff and their ability of inspiring trust (Zeithaml and Bitner, 2003);
- **Empathy** resides on the manner in which the communication between academics and students is performed.

Each dimension comprises various elements, with some of them being exemplified, in a less exhaustive manner, as it follows:

- The tangibles dimension includes statements regarding the endowment level of spaces dedicated to both teaching and recreational activities, the existence of state-of-the-art equipment and technologies, the generosity of the library's book offer, attractiveness of informative materials (brochures, files etc.);
- The reliability dimension comprises statements that enable determining student's satisfaction with the university's interest for promptly solving the promised services, the educational process's conformity with the academic regulations, the correspondence between university's offers and students' needs;
- Responsiveness collects information regarding the level of informing the student about various aspects related to the academic community, if the lectures are taught according to students' understanding level and adapted to the requirement of the labor market, if the students are satisfied with the schedule;
- Assurance seeks to remark the positive attitude of the academic staff, teaching the courses with the help of attractive materials, supporting student's critically thinking;
- Empathy groups statements about encouraging the communication between the academic staff and the student, active participation in class through developing team-work abilities, easy access to information about the faculty (notice board, website), support from the university for solving student's individual problems.

The difference between the average of customers' perceptions and the average of customers' expectations reflects the quality level of the delivered service. The results are compared in order to identify the magnitude of gaps for each dimension. A large gap shows the low quality of that service, while a small gap reflects the service's good quality (Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1994).

Results

A previous study determined high satisfaction rates among students from Central Asia that studied abroad at universities from various countries like Russia, United Kingdom, Kyrgyzstan, Turkey, China, United States of America, Malaysia, Czech Republic, Germany, Netherlands, France, Canada, South Korea, Austria, Belarus, Ukraine, Australia, Ireland and Norway. These students' high satisfaction was largely attributed to the level of physical facilities found especially in the ITC area and in the universities' libraries (specific elements of the tangibles dimension), but also to the relevance of academic courses at which the investigated students participated for their future perspectives on the labor market (the assurance dimension) (Sabatayeva et al., 2018). In the same context one can place the opinion of foreign students who opted to study at universities in Canada and which had the same perception regarding tangibles, but also showed a high appreciation for the assurance dimension found in the services provided by the higher education institutions (Yasin and Belanger, 2015). Another study revealed that foreign students studying in Malaysia are very satisfied with the physical facilities, especially those related to ITC, but also with the superior courses and the expertise of the academic staff (the assurance dimension). However, the investigated students had a double recommendation for the university: to focus more on solving students' individual problems (the empathy dimension) and to promptly and professionally provide the promised services (the reliability dimension) (Ong, 2013).

Impressed with the physical facilities offered by the university were the international students in Singapore as well, but unlike the others, they had higher expectancies for the assurance dimension (Min, Khoon and Tan, 2012). The importance of higher education institutions' investments in IT facilities for improving students' satisfaction was also in line with the results of other studies (Mai, 2005).

At the opposite pole are the overseas students studying in universities from United States of America, which presented a novel situation. The satisfaction of international students from universities in Indiana and Michigan seems to be positively influenced as long as there are reliability and empathy. In other words, there is a high impact on their experience as long as they find at their host university communication, interest for solving the problems they face individually and solving problems as quickly as possible (the reliability and empathy dimensions). They seemed less preoccupied with specific tangibles aspects like the aspect and maintenance of installations, equipment and staff (Ongo, 2019).

A study conducted in the United Kingdom, a country whose universities are preferred by students coming from all over the world, comes to emphasize some of the previous results. This research

identified that the assurance dimension represents the basis for foreign students' satisfaction. Moreover, they considered that a university's consistent reputation is built through both the provided physical facilities and the interaction between students and the academic staff (Onwumere, 2018).

Becoming more and more aware that students are demanding consumers of educational programs and that measures should be adopted for the continuous improvement of provided services, the higher education in South Africa closely follows those in UK and Australia in what concerns the development of external agencies for quality assurance. Previous research shows that students studying in this country are satisfied with the physical facilities they find in the university and with the advice received when they arrive at the university, but they wish for their requirements to be solved more quickly, for the environment to be friendlier and for the staff to be able to adapt according to the problems that arise from the perspective of intercultural and language differences (the assurance and empathy dimensions) (Noel, 2011).

Previous analysis of students that have come to study in Scotland revealed the following elements as being important for outlining their expectations regarding the quality of the educational service (Essam, Wang and Hassan, 2013):

1. The staff should be willing to help both from the teaching perspective and at a personal level (the responsiveness dimension);
2. The university should be willing to solve students' problems and preoccupations (the reliability dimension);
3. The academic staff should be fair and consistent in assessing students' materials (the reliability dimension);
4. The tuition fee should reflect the quality of all services provided by the higher education institution.

The first three aspects mentioned above come to emphasize the conclusions of another study, showing that students coming from different cultures can have different opinions when assessing the provided service, but their attitude is the same when it comes to reliability and staff's responsiveness (Furrer, Liu and Sudharshan, 2000).

A different situation was revealed by a study conducted in seven universities from the United Arab Emirates, as the investigated students externalized their dissatisfaction with all the dimensions of the SERVQUAL model. This reflects student's strong disappointment with the services provided by these universities. A large gap was recorded especially regarding the assurance dimension, as there exists mistrust in universities' abilities to provide career opportunities on the labor market, because most of the institutions are just campuses of universities from other countries and there was no collaboration between the academic environment and industry. The smaller gap between the scores for services' quality was registered for the empathy dimension, as students were satisfied with the care and attention shown by the university, although they came from different cultures. The investigated students revealed a hierarchy for prioritizing university's efforts for increasing reputation, containing the dimensions in the following order: reliability, assurance and responsiveness and less for the tangibles and empathy dimensions (Datta and Vardhan, 2017). If the international students studying in the United Arab Emirates were most satisfied with the empathy expressed by the staff in the host universities, in universities from Turkey the sensitive areas detected by the investigated students consisted precisely in the weak support they perceived receiving from the university personnel, especially from the non-academic staff (Bozbay et al., 2020).

Another study revealed that with the support of the Chinese government, Chinese universities are strongly oriented to attracting a high as possible number of international students and they therefore offer attractive incentives in the form of scholarships, that can be governmental, provincial and presidential. In what concerns the satisfaction of international students in China, it is emphasized that this is based more on specific elements for the dimensions of tangibles, empathy and reliability and less on the assurance and responsiveness dimensions (Zaineldeen, Hongbo and Ibrahim, 2020).

In universities from Japan the international students' preoccupation for meeting competent academics (the responsiveness dimension) was noticed, while students considered that the academic program should be designed and formulated according to the international standards (the reliability dimension). Moreover, it is expected for the staff to be proactive in providing the promised services (the reliability dimension). At the same time, it was emphasized that advertisement and recommendations of former

beneficiaries of these programs represent stimuli for students when choosing a university program (Sultan and Wong, 2010).

An interesting aspect was noticed following a research conducted in Barcelona. In this case, the trigger element for the international student's satisfaction was empathy. The student seemed very impressed with the interest shown by the university for the problems he faces during his studies, for facilitating him access to the important information. Students' expectations for the future show that they expect an increasing interest of the university in the direction of elements included in the tangibility, reliability and assurance dimensions (Mongay, 2014).

Discussion and conclusions

Comparing the expectations and perceptions of international students from different year of studies can generate additional important information for a better guidance of the actions for improving the quality of higher education. The SERVQUAL represents a helpful instrument in this direction, because it enables identifying those strategic areas for which triggering measures should be implemented in order to raise the quality level of educational services.

Analyzing studies conducted by various researchers in universities located in different countries has enabled the outlining of some measures, that can generate a reduction of the gaps that affect the satisfaction of the student studying abroad and which can have as effect even reaching a stage that corresponds to students' requirements from the perspective of SERVQUAL model's dimensions:

1. Focusing resources for buying new equipment, in order to ensure facilities that are physically maintained and visually appealing. This aspect is supported by the majority of previous referred studies, which demonstrate a very high impact of the tangibles dimension on the satisfaction of students studying abroad.
2. Implementation of the university management of a culture of high-quality services in the institution. For this goal, the staff should be trained to know the technology at the workplace, to have a digital education, such that it can reach high standards of efficiency and performance. The staff should have capabilities that enable understanding students' problems, both from the academic and the administrative areas, which are mostly generated by the different cultures where they come from (the assurance dimension).
3. A strong determinant factor for the investigated international students' satisfaction is assurance. Improvement of this dimension can be obtained through establishing a support service that keeps a direct and permanent contact with the students and their problems; in case this service does not work, higher level decision makers should be notified.
4. The reliability dimension that was mentioned many times in the analyzed studies and that represents for Parasuraman the most important dimension in order to reach a high level of student satisfaction, can be improved through implementing a mechanism for checking the time frames that were promised to students and the existence of a system that monitors students' feedback.

Synthesizing the previously mentioned aspects, it can be stated that the existence of communication channels between university and student, that enable promptly recording the gaps in the relationship between these two parts, can become viable managerial instruments through which university management can correctly and timely control and assess the situation regarding the quality level of the provided services. This way the decision factors are connected to students' problems and focusing on solving these problems can turn into a true competitive advantage.

It is therefore absolutely necessary for universities to be interested in evolving in a sustained manner, in enabling a better understanding of intercultural differences, in being in accord with the standardization degree and at the same time, in taking into account service customization.

The development of this preoccupations will obviously generate the existence of advanced educational services, which together with high quality health services, will enable a nation to have a high development level from economic, social, but also cultural point of views (Săvoiu et al., 2014).

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